

Soil organic carbon sequestration potential for croplands in Finland over 2021–2040 under the interactive impacts of climate change and agricultural management

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HIGHLIGHTS

- IPCC tier 3 approach was applied to quantify cropland SOC sequestration potential.
- 20% increase in C input would not be enough to meet the 4‰ target over 2021–2040.
- Climate change would reduce SOC sequestration on average by 0.28 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.
- 20% additional C input is not enough to compensate climate change impact on SOC.
- Contribution of C input, temperature, precipitation to SOC sequestration is 56%, 24%, and 20%.

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ABSTRACT

CONTEXT: Cropland soil organic carbon (SOC) stock can be increased by agricultural management, but is subject to various factors. The extent and rates of SOC sequestration potential, as well as the controlling factors, under different climate and management practices across a region or country are important for policy-makers and land managers, however have been rarely known.

OBJECTIVE: We aim to investigate the extent and rates of SOC sequestration potential over 2021–2040 under different scenarios of climate change and Sustainable Soil Management (SSM) practices, and quantify the impacts of climate change and SSM practices on the SOC sequestration potential, for croplands across Finland at a spatial resolution of 1 km.

METHODS: RothC model is run iteratively to equilibrium to calculate the size of the SOC pools and the annual plant carbon inputs. Then, it is applied to investigate the SOC sequestration potential over 2021–2040 under different scenarios of climate change and SSM practices. Finally, factorial simulation experiments are conducted to quantify the impacts of climate change and SSM practices, alone and in combination, on SOC sequestration potential.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION: Under the combined impacts of climate change and SSM practices, the SOC sequestration potential during 2021–2040 relative to 2020 will be on average –0.03, 0.007, 0.05, and 0.13 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, respectively, with carbon input being business as usual, 5%, 10%, and 20% increase. This is equivalent to an annual change rate of –0.04%, 0.009%, 0.07%, and 0.17%, respectively. Therefore, a 20% increase in C input to soil will not be enough to obtain a 4‰ increase per year over the 20-year period in Finland. Carbon input will promote SOC sequestration potential; however, climate change will reduce it on average by 0.28 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Across the cropland in Finland, on average, the relative contributions of C input, temperature, and precipitation to SOC sequestration potential in 2021–2040 will be 56%, 24%, and 20%, respectively, however there is a spatially explicit pattern. The SOC sequestration potential will be relatively high and dominated by C input in west and southwest Finland. By contrast, it will be relatively low and dominated by climate in north and east Finland, and the central part of southern Finland.

SIGNIFICANCE: Our findings provide the information as to where, how much, and which SSM practices could be applied for enhancing SOC sequestration at a high spatial resolution, which is essential for stakeholders to increase cropland SOC sequestration efficiently.

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1. Introduction

Soil is the largest terrestrial pool of organic carbon (C) (Scharlemann et al., 2014). The stock of soil organic C (SOC) over a depth of 2 m is about 2400 Gt C, about three times the amount of C in the atmosphere and four times the biotic C pool (Lal, 2004; Sanderman et al., 2017). According to the “4 per 1000” initiative, an annual increase of “4 per 1000” (0.4%) of organic matter in all soils globally to a depth of 40 cm will be enough to compensate for the human-induced global emissions of CO₂ (<http://4p1000.org/understand>). Maintaining and increasing SOC stocks are not only crucial for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions but also for soil health, fertility and food security (FAO, 2017).

Cropland SOC stocks are subject to environmental factors (i.e., temperature, soil moisture, soil properties) and agricultural management practices such as inputs of crop residues, organic manure and fertilizers, irrigation and tillage managements (Lal, 2006; Lal et al., 2018; Tao et al., 2019). Extensive studies have investigated cropland SOC dynamics and their controlling factors in broad regions of the world using soil measurements (Heikkinen et al., 2013, 2021), meta-analyses (Jian et al., 2020; Matus, 2021), empirical or process-based soil C models (Smith et al., 2005; Lugato et al., 2015; Launay et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2021). These studies show that temperature increase accelerates SOC decomposition rate, leading to a positive climate-carbon cycle feedback. Precipitation affects SOC decomposition rate by increasing soil water content in the topsoil (Jenkinson et al., 1992; Jenkinson and Coleman, 1994). SOC is bound to the fine fractions of silt and clay and stabilized in the soil by the formation of organo-mineral complexes (Matus, 2021). Improved fertilization practices, soil tillage practices, and crop management practices could increase global C sequestration potential by 0.44–0.68 Gt C yr⁻¹, assuming maximum complementarity among all measures taken (Lessmann et al., 2022). The spatiotemporal changes in cropland SOC stocks in the past decades were diverse and soil C sink capacity depended on land use, the antecedent SOC stock, climate, clay content and mineralogy, and agricultural management (Lal et al., 2018; Lessmann et al., 2022). For example, in Finland carbon concentration of the cultivated soils decreased continuously on average by 0.2–0.3% yr⁻¹ relative to the existing carbon concentration for organic soils and 0.4% yr⁻¹ or 220 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for mineral soils over 1974–2009 based on soil samples measurements, mainly owing to increasing cultivation of annual crops, climatic change, and land use change legacy (conversion from forest) (Heikkinen et al., 2013, 2022). In contrast, the SOC stocks in The Netherlands (Reijneveld et al., 2009) and Sweden (Poeplau et al., 2015) increased. And no significant changes in SOC stocks were detected for Germany (Umweltbundesamt, 2016).

Besides the SOC changes and their mechanisms in the past decades, the extent and rates of SOC sequestration potential under different land use and management practices in a region or country are equally important information for policy-makers and land managers. There is an urgent need to identify which regions, environments and agricultural systems present the greatest potential for increasing SOC stocks, and which Sustainable Soil Management (SSM) practices are suitable and cost-efficient for a specific environment (FAO, 2020). Mean annual SOC sequestration rates (t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) can be determined by dividing SOC changes by the duration of the defined period. The SOC sequestration rates vary greatly depending on soil characteristics, management, and climate (Smith et al., 2008; Lal et al., 2018) because they are affected by C inputs from crop residues and C lost from the soils through soil erosion and decomposition processes, as well as the longevity and persistence of soil C (Paustian et al., 2019). Representing the heterogeneity of these key factors and production systems at a high resolution across a region or country is one of the main methodological challenges when attempting to estimate SOC sequestration (Lal, 2004). The use of process-based soil carbon models to integrate various local high resolution spatiotemporal databases such as land cover, soil properties, climate, and C inputs can address this challenge (Tribouillois et al.,

2018). This method is encouraged by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) as higher order methods (tier 3) but realized in only few countries (IPCC, 2019; Smith et al., 2020). In addition, the process-based modeling has the advantage of being able to simulate both climate change and agricultural management scenarios and to investigate their interactive impacts on SOC sequestration in the past and the future (Tribouillois et al., 2018). Owing to a dearth of data and difficulties in integrated modeling (Brilli et al., 2017), however, few studies have applied this approach to large spatial and temporal scales to estimate the past, current and future potential SOC sequestration (Lugato et al., 2015; Launay et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2021). Along this line, recently there are increasing interests to apply process-based models to assess the potential of agricultural practices to sequester C. For example, the CENTURY agroecosystem model was applied to assess the SOC sequestration rates of six alternative management practices scenarios for pan-European to support possible carbon sequestration policies (Lugato et al., 2015). The STICS model was applied to quantify SOC storage potential, greenhouse gas (GHG) balance, biomass production and nitrogen- and water-related impacts for cropland in France for current cropping systems and three mitigation scenarios (Launay et al., 2021). A reverse RothC modeling approach was applied to estimate the amount of C inputs to soils required to sustain current SOC stocks and to increase them by 4‰ per year over a period of 30 years for France (Martin et al., 2021). The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) is coordinating the Global assessment of SOC sequestration potential (GSOSeq) programme to develop SOC Sequestration Potential maps at 1 km resolution for croplands using the RothC model (FAO, 2020). However, such studies and information have rarely been available so far in Finland.

Located in the Nordic region, Finland is projected to experience more severe climate change, and therefore adaptation and mitigation have been of key concern in the nation (Regina et al., 2019; Wiréhn et al., 2020). Finland aims to achieve the goal of carbon neutrality by 2035 and be carbon negative soon after that, one of the most ambitious policies globally. However, carbon concentration of the cultivated soils in Finland decreased continuously over the past decades (Heikkinen et al., 2013, 2022; Akujärvi et al., 2014; Palosuo et al., 2016). The SOC-to-fine-fraction ratio had stabilized and the changes in SOC content leveled off in fields with long cultivation history (>100 years) (Heikkinen et al., 2022). Although climate change results in the SOC loss, improved management practices can promote SOC sequestration and compensate the C losses at least partly (Heikkinen et al., 2022). How to manage croplands to build SOC sequestration over the coming decades under climate change and agricultural management has been of key concern (Hakala et al., 2016; Regina et al., 2019). Therefore, the objectives of this study are to use a model-based approach together with various local high-resolution datasets to (i) investigate the SOC sequestration potential over 2021–2040 under different scenarios of climate change and SSM practices, and (ii) quantify the impacts of climate change and SSM practices, alone and in combination, on the SOC sequestration potential, for croplands across Finland at a spatial resolution of 1 km.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study areas

The study area covers the current croplands across Finland, with the continental subarctic or boreal climates in Köppen climate classification (Geiger, 1954). Only the croplands with mineral soils are investigated in this study, with organic soil (i.e., peat layer >30 cm) masked from croplands. The southern coast is humid continental with mild summer, wet all year, and the rest of the country is subarctic with cool summer, wet all year. The annual average temperature ranges from 5.0 °C to 7.5 °C in southwest Finland, with quite mild winters and warm summers, and ranges from 0 °C to –4 °C in the northeast (<https://www.weather-atlas.com/en/finland-climate>). The annual rainfall ranges from 483 mm to 584 mm in the northern region, 584 mm to 711 mm in the south.

The rainfall occurs throughout the year and is highest in July and August. Half of the annual precipitation in the north falls as snow. According to WRB classification (FAO, 1998), the Finnish cultivated soils are mostly Cambisols (34%), Podzols (27%), Regosols (19%), and Histosols (10%) (Lilja et al., 2006). The area of cropland has increased by about 50% from 1910 to 2010 in Finland and the cultivation areas of annual crops have also increased (Agricultural Statistics, 2021). Nowadays, cropland, about 2.3 million hectares, accounts for around 8% of land area. Area of cereal crops cover is approximately one million hectares, about 50% of Finland's field area. The staple crops include wheat, barley, oats, and rye. Agriculture is mainly rainfed. The mean plant carbon inputs into soils during the past decades have been estimated to vary from 1.7 to 2.4 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in the croplands across Finland, depending on crop species (Palosuo et al., 2016). Annual crops are typically sown in spring and harvested in autumn, although autumn-sown varieties are increasing. Machinery is heavily applied. Pesticide and inorganic fertilizers applications have increased, slurry application has increased whereas farmyard manure has decreased. Since the C/N ratio for cattle slurry and farmyard manure is about 2 and 13 (Shah et al., 2020), it has more potential to increase SOC per unit manure added (Mori, 2018; Shah et al., 2020). More conservative cultivation practices are becoming common. The cultivated area under no-till or reduced tillage systems in years 2015 and 2016 was 38% (Agricultural Statistics, 2021).

2.2. RothC soil carbon model

RothC is a model for organic carbon turnover in non-waterlogged topsoil, accounting for the effects of soil type, temperature, moisture content and plant cover on the turnover process (Jenkinson et al., 1992; Jenkinson and Coleman, 1994). It has been tested and applied in wide regions including the Nordic conditions (e.g., Falloon and Smith, 2002; Peltre et al., 2012). It calculates total organic carbon (t C ha⁻¹) and microbial biomass carbon (t C ha⁻¹) at a monthly time step on a time-scale of years to centuries. In the model, SOC is split into four active compartments and inert organic matter (IOM). The four active compartments are decomposable plant material (DPM), resistant plant material (RPM), microbial biomass (BIO) and humified organic matter (HUM). Each compartment decomposes by a first-order process with its own characteristic rate, which is modified by temperature, moisture, and soil cover rate.

(Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996). Incoming plant carbon is split between DPM and RPM, depending on the DPM/RPM ratio of the particular incoming plant material. A DPM/RPM ratio of 1.44 was applied for most agricultural crops and improved grassland (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996). For the farmyard manure, 49% goes to the DPM, 49% goes to the RPM, and 2% goes to the HUM compartment. Soil clay content affects the stabilization of SOC by determining the ratio between the CO₂ and BIO + HUM produced.

2.3. Data

RothC requires data on monthly precipitation, mean temperature and potential evapotranspiration, soil clay content, soil cover, and C input into soil. Monthly precipitation and mean temperature data from 1981 to 2019 across Finland at a spatial resolution of 10 km × 10 km are obtained from Finland Meteorological Institute (Aalto et al., 2016). Monthly potential evapotranspiration from 1981 to 2019 at a spatial resolution of 4 × 4 km² is obtained from the TerraClimate which is a dataset of monthly climate and climatic water balance for global terrestrial surfaces (Abatzoglou et al., 2018). Soil clay content is obtained from the SoilGrids250m dataset, in which clay content (0–2 micro meter) mass fraction in percentage at seven standard depths is predicted using the global compilation of soil ground observations (Hengl et al., 2017) (Fig.S1). The Terra Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Vegetation Indices 16-Day (MOD13A2)

Version 6.1 product provides vegetation index values at a per pixel basis at 1 km spatial resolution. The Normalized difference in vegetation index (NDVI) from MOD13A2 over 1981–2019 is used to determine if soil was bare (NDVI ≤ 0.6) or vegetated (NDVI > 0.6) in a particular month. The Global dataset of land cover from European Space Agency (www.esa-landcover-cci.org) is applied and reclassified into the FAO Global Land Cover (FAO, 2020) since there is no better land use map for Finland at 1 km spatial resolution.

Five climate scenarios for 2021–2040 are obtained from five global circulation models (GCMs) including GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, and UKESM1-0-LL in the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) experiment (O'Neill et al., 2016). Climate variables include daily maximum air temperature, minimum air temperature, wind speed, air pressure, and relative air humidity. The potential evapotranspiration for 2021–2040 is calculated by the Penman-Monteith method using the daily projections. The outputs driven by the high-end emission scenario of Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) 8.5 are adopted and bias-corrected using the monthly temperature and precipitation (Aalto et al., 2016) and PET (Abatzoglou et al., 2018) from 1981 to 2000 (Fig.S2).

2.4. Methods to estimate C input under business as usual management practices

Since robust estimate of C input is critical to simulate SOC stock dynamics however difficult at a high resolution across a country (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996; Smith et al., 2005). In this study, C input under business as usual (BAU) management practices is estimated at a resolution of 1 km using two representative approaches to account for its uncertainty. One is to estimate C input based on Net Primary Production (NPP) calculated from the MIAMI model (NPP_m) (Lieth, 1975) and multiplied by a coefficient of 0.53 for cropland and 0.72 for grassland which are approximate proportion of NPP that ends up in the soil (Schulze et al., 2010). The other approach is to estimate C input based on crop yield and livestock statistics (C_{in}^{yield&livestock}). Soil C input consists of C input from above-ground biomass, below-ground (root) biomass, and livestock manure. Above-ground biomass and below-ground biomass of crops are calculated based on the national yield statistics of main crops at a prefecture level (Agricultural Statistics, 2021) following Bolinder et al. (2007) but with Finland national parameters on the harvest index and the ratio of shoot and root biomass of main crops (Hakala et al., 2016). C input from above-ground biomass (C_{AG}) is calculated as:

$$C_{AG} = (BM_{AG} - BM_Y) \times C_{BM} \quad (1)$$

where BM_{AG} is above-ground biomass, BM_Y is grain yield biomass, and C_{BM} is C content of dry biomass (45%). We thus assume no straw removal to take place.

C input from belowground biomass (C_{BG}) was calculated as:

$$C_{BG} = BM_{BG} \times \left(\frac{1}{RL} + TR \right) \times C_{BM} \quad (2)$$

where BM_{BG} is below-ground biomass, RL is the length (years) of the crop rotation (one for annual crops and 3.5 for perennial crops), and TR is the root turnover rate (1/year), taking 0.41 as previous studies (Gill and Jackson, 2000; Kuzyakov and Domanski, 2000; Gill et al., 2002; Nguyen, 2003; Kuzyakov and Schneckengerger, 2004; Palosuo et al., 2016).

Organic matter in livestock manure consisting of biodegradable and nonbiodegradable fractions is known as volatile solids (Appuhamy et al., 2018). As Palosuo et al. (2016), manure-derived C input (C_{manure}) is calculated as:

$$C_{manure} = \sum_i N_i \times VS_i \times C_{manure} \quad (3)$$

where N_i is the number of head of each livestock specie i , VS_i is the average annual excretion of volatile solids in manure per head of species i . C content of manure (C_{manure}) was assumed to be 50% of annual excretion of volatile solids (Pettygrove et al., 2009).

2.5. Modeling protocol

Based on the GSOSeq Global Soil Organic Carbon Sequestration Potential Map Technical Manual (FAO, 2020), for each pixel, the RothC model is run at three phases consecutively, including a long spin-up run for 1000 years, a warm-up run for 2001–2020, and a forward run for 2021–2040. In the long spin-up run, monthly average temperature, precipitation and PET during 1981–2000 are input, RothC is run iteratively to calculate the size of the SOC pools and the annual plant carbon inputs using the monthly average climate conditions but with C input for each pixel updated yearly using the estimated C input (C_{eq}) for the previous year from eq. (4) until theoretical equilibrium is reached when all SOC pools stabilize (Smith et al., 2005). With the iterative method, C_{eq} is updated yearly using eq. (4) and input into the model as C input until the results of the long spin-up fit the estimates of total SOC stocks of 0–30 cm provided in the FAO-ITPS GSOSeqmap (i.e., $SOC_{sim} = SOC_{GSOSeq}$) (Smith et al., 2005; FAO and ITPS, 2020; FAO, 2020) as:

$$C_{eq} = C_i \times \frac{SOC_{GSOSeq} - IOM}{SOC_{sim} - IOM} \quad (4)$$

where C_{eq} is the estimated annual C input before and at equilibrium ($t \text{ C ha}^{-1}$), C_i is the initial annual C addition, which is set to be 1 t C ha^{-1} in the first equilibrium run (the initial value does not matter much) and thereafter is updated yearly using the estimated C_{eq} for the previous year. SOC_{GSOSeq} is the estimated soil C given in the FAO-ITPS GSOSeqmap, SOC_{sim} is the RothC-simulated soil C for each year. IOM is the C content of the inert organic matter fraction in the soil. The IOM fraction ($t \text{ C ha}^{-1}$) is set as Falloon and Smith (2002):

$$IOM = 0.049 \times (SOC_{GSOSeq})^{1.139} \quad (5)$$

The 1000-year long spin-up run results finally in the estimated C_{eq} and the size of the different SOC pools ($t \text{ Cha}^{-1}$) in year 2000. In the warm-up run, the interannual changes in C inputs from 2000 are adjusted according to changes in NPP (Smith et al., 2005; FAO, 2020) as Eqs. (6) and (7):

$$BAU_{C2001} = C_{eq} \times \frac{NPP_{2001}}{NPP_{1981-2000}} \quad (6)$$

where BAU_{C2001} the annual carbon input for the first year of the ‘warm-up’ phase (i.e., 2001). $NPP_{1981-2000}$ is the estimated average NPP_m or $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ over the initialization period (1981–2000); and NPP_{2001} is the estimated annual NPP_m or $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ for the first year of the ‘warm-up’ phase.

$$BAU_{Ct} = C_{t-1} \times \frac{NPP_t}{NPP_{t-1}} \quad (7)$$

where BAU_{Ct} is the annual C input of a specific year t after 2001; C_{t-1} is the annual C input of the previous year; NPP_t is the NPP_m or $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ of year t , and NPP_{t-1} is the NPP_m or $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ of the previous year (in $t \text{ C ha}^{-1}$).

In the warm-up run and forward run, we set six modeling experiments with different settings of C input and climate (Table 1) to quantify the impacts of climate change and agricultural management on SOC sequestration, alone and in combination.

As shown in Table 1, in the modeling experiment 1 ($E1_{npp.0120}$), annual C input estimated from yearly NPP_m and the monthly climate data from 2001 to 2020 are applied in the warm-up phase; and annual C input estimated from yearly NPP_m and the monthly average climate during 2001–2020 are applied in the forward modeling. The modeling

experiment 2 ($E2_{npp.2140}$) uses the same settings as $E1_{npp.0120}$ except that the monthly average climate during 2021–2040 based on the climate scenarios are applied in the forward modeling. The modeling experiment 3 ($E3_{yield.0120}$) uses the same settings as $E1_{npp.0120}$ except that the $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ (i.e., Eqs. (1)–(3)) is applied in both the warm-up phase and the forward modeling. The modeling experiment 4 ($E4_{yield.2140}$) use the same settings as $E3_{yield.0120}$ except that the monthly average climate during 2021–2040 based on the climate scenarios is applied in the forward modeling. The modeling experiment 5 ($E5_{nppyr.2140}$) uses the same settings as $E2_{npp.2140}$ except that the yearly NPP_m during 2021–2040 estimated using the five future climate scenarios is applied in the forward modeling. Thus future climate change impacts on the yearly NPP_m during 2021–2040 are incorporated. The modeling experiment 6 ($E6_{yieldyr.2140}$) uses the same settings as $E4_{yield.2140}$ except that the yearly $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ during 2021–2040 is applied in the forward modeling. So the expected changes in $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ during 2021–2040 are incorporated. The $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ during 2021–2040 is estimated by multiplying a factor of 1.22 based on its yearly increase rate of 1.1% from 1990 to 2020, as well as the projected crop yield change (Tao et al., 2015), in Finland.

Based on the six modeling experiments (Table 1), the impacts of climate change (agricultural management) on SOC sequestration are quantified by the relative changes in the simulated SOC stocks between $E2_{npp.2140}$ and $E1_{npp.0120}$ ($E5_{nppyr.2140}$ and $E2_{npp.2140}$), and $E4_{yield.2140}$ and $E3_{yield.0120}$ ($E6_{yieldyr.2140}$ and $E4_{yield.2140}$). The integrated impacts of climate change and agricultural management on SOC sequestration are quantified by the relative changes in the simulated SOC stocks between $E5_{nppyr.2140}$ and $E1_{npp.0120}$ under the C input based on NPP_m , and $E6_{yieldyr.2140}$ and $E3_{yield.0120}$ under the C input based on $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$.

For the simulations using the future climate scenario, the five climate scenarios are applied respectively to account for the uncertainties from

Table 1
Settings for modeling experiments in this study.

Experiment	Warm-up (2001–2020)		Forward modeling (2021–2040)	
	C input	Climate	C input	Climate
$E1_{npp.0120}$	Yearly NPP_m from 2001 to 2020	Monthly climate data from 2001 to 2020	Yearly NPP_m from 2001 to 2020 derived by MIAMI model	Monthly average climate during 2001–2020
$E2_{npp.2140}$	Yearly NPP_m from 2001 to 2020	Monthly climate data from 2001 to 2020	Yearly NPP_m from 2001 to 2020 derived by MIAMI model	Monthly average climate scenario during 2021–2040
$E3_{yield.0120}$	Yearly $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ from 2001 to 2020	Monthly climate data from 2001 to 2020	Yearly $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ from 2001 to 2020	Monthly average climate during 2001–2020
$E4_{yield.2140}$	Yearly $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ from 2001 to 2020	Monthly climate data from 2001 to 2020	Yearly $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ from 2001 to 2020	Monthly average climate scenario during 2021–2040
$E5_{nppyr.2140}$	Yearly NPP_m from 2001 to 2020	Monthly climate data from 2001 to 2020	Yearly NPP_m from 2021 to 2040 derived by MIAMI model	Monthly average climate scenario during 2021–2040
$E6_{yieldyr.2140}$	Yearly $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ from 2001 to 2020	Monthly climate data from 2001 to 2020	Yearly $Cin_{yield\&livestock}$ from 2021 to 2040	Monthly average climate scenario during 2021–2040

climate scenarios. And the median of the five simulated results is adopted for each pixel. The expected SSM practices over 2021–2040 are grouped into three management scenarios (SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3) based on their expected relative effects on C input compared to BAU (i. e., C input adopt NPP_m or $C_{in,yield\&livestock}$). The expected effects of SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3 scenarios are set as 5%, 10%, and 20% increase in C inputs, respectively, relative to BAU (FAO, 2020). The use of multiple SSMs instead of one allows stakeholders to understand SOC sequestration efficiency of C inputs and develop cost-effective management practices. The C input increase can be realized by various agronomic management practices which will be determined by local stakeholders and is beyond the focus of this study.

2.6. Analyses

2.6.1. Calculating the absolute SOC sequestration and relative SOC sequestration

The absolute SOC sequestration (ΔSOC_A) for a time period relative to the year 2020 is determined for BAU and SSM practices as:

$$\Delta SOC_{A,t,i} = SOC_{t,i} - SOC_{t0,i} \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta SOC_{A,t,i}$ ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$) refers to the absolute SOC sequestration at a time t (the year 2040 in this study) relative to a time $t0$ (the year 2020 in this study) under agricultural management scenario i (BAU, SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3 in this study). $SOC_{t,i}$ and $SOC_{t0,i}$ refer to the simulated SOC stock at a time t and $t0$ under agricultural management scenario i .

The relative SOC sequestration (ΔSOC_R) comparing to BAU for a time period is determined for SSM practices as:

$$\Delta SOC_{R,t,i} = SOC_{t,i} - SOC_{t,BAU} \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta SOC_{R,t,i}$ ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$) refers to the relative SOC sequestration for a time period t (2021–2040 in this study) under agricultural management scenario i (SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3 in this study), comparing to BAU. $SOC_{t,i}$ and $SOC_{t,BAU}$ refer to the simulated SOC stock at a time t under agricultural management scenario i and BAU, respectively.

Mean annual absolute (ΔSOC_{ASR}) or relative (ΔSOC_{RSR}) SOC sequestration rate per year ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) are determined by dividing SOC changes (ΔSOC_A or ΔSOC_R) by the duration of the defined period (20 years from 2021 to 2040 in this study). The period of 20 years is considered a representative period to assess medium-term impacts on SOC (Lessmann et al., 2022).

2.6.2. The relative contribution of temperature, precipitation and C input to SOC sequestration rate

For each pixel, we conduct a multiple linear regression between the simulated ΔSOC_{ASR} (Y) and temperature (T), precipitation (P), and C input (C_{in}) as Eq. (10), based on the total 40 simulations (5 climate scenarios \times 4 agricultural managements \times 2C inputs) in the modeling experiment $E5_{NPPyr.2140}$ and $E6_{yield\&livestock.2140}$. Then, the regression coefficients for $T(\alpha)$, $P(\beta)$ and $C_{in}(\gamma)$ are standardized as α' , β' and γ' for comparisons based on the standard deviation of $T(S_T)$, $P(S_P)$, $C_{in}(S_{Cin})$ and $\Delta SOC_{ASR}(S_Y)$ using Eqs. (11)–(13), respectively. Finally, the relative contribution of temperature (T_{rc}), precipitation (P_{rc}), and C input (C_{inrc}) to the ΔSOC_{ASR} is calculated using Eqs. (14)–(16), respectively.

$$Y = \alpha T + \beta P + \gamma C_{in} + \delta \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha' = \alpha \frac{S_T}{S_Y} \quad (11)$$

$$\beta' = \beta \frac{S_P}{S_Y} \quad (12)$$

$$\gamma' = \gamma \frac{S_{Cin}}{S_Y} \quad (13)$$

$$T_{rc} = \frac{|\alpha'|}{|\alpha'| + |\beta'| + |\gamma'|} \quad (14)$$

$$P_{rc} = \frac{|\beta'|}{|\alpha'| + |\beta'| + |\gamma'|} \quad (15)$$

$$C_{inrc} = \frac{|\gamma'|}{|\alpha'| + |\beta'| + |\gamma'|} \quad (16)$$

2.6.3. Assessing the uncertainty in estimating SOC sequestration

As FAO (2020), the uncertainty (%) in estimating SOC sequestration from model inputs of monthly temperature, monthly precipitation, soil clay content, SOC from the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap, and C input is estimated for each SSM and climate change scenario as:

$$Uncertainty = \frac{100 \times (SOC_{max} - SOC_{min})}{2 \times SOC} \quad (17)$$

where SOC refers to the average simulated SOC stocks in each pixel, for each climate and SSM scenario, after 20 years of the forward modeling phase. SOC_{max} ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$) refers to the upper limit of simulated SOC stocks for each pixel and SOC_{min} ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$) refers to the lower limit of simulated SOC stocks. As Hastings et al. (2010) and FAO (2020), SOC_{max} for each pixel is derived by the simulated SOC stocks with model inputs of monthly temperature, monthly precipitation, soil clay content, SOC from the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap, and C input multiplied by 1.02, 1.05, 1.10, 1.2, and 1.15, respectively. SOC_{min} for each pixel is derived by the simulated SOC stocks with model inputs of monthly temperature, monthly precipitation, soil clay content, SOC from the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap, and C input multiplied by 0.98, 0.95, 0.90, 0.8, and 0.85, respectively. Although the uncertainty coefficients for the key model inputs are determined arbitrarily to some extent following FAO (2020), using the general uncertainty coefficients is an effective method to roughly investigate the output uncertainty when the uncertainty information on model inputs is missing (Hastings et al., 2010; FAO, 2020). Considered that the quality of model inputs data in this study is higher than that in FAO (2020), using the uncertainty coefficients is conservative.

3. Results

3.1. Spatiotemporal pattern of C input based on the two approaches

After the long spin-up run, the estimated annual C input at equilibrium in 2000 ranges from 0.90 to 3.81 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ with an average of 1.51 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ (Fig. 1a). The high C input is mainly located in west and southwest Finland and south coast areas, and the low input is in the central part of south Finland (Fig. 1a). The C input in 2001–2020 based on NPP_m approach ranges from 0.94 to 3.99 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ with an average of 1.59 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ across the pixels (Fig. 1b). It is slightly higher but with a similar pattern compared with the C input at equilibrium (Fig. 1a, b). The median C input in 2021–2040 based on NPP_m is projected to range from 0.98 to 4.06 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ with an average of 1.67 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$, using the five future climate scenarios (Fig. 1c). The C input is projected to increase generally across Finland in 2021–2040, particularly in southwest and south Finland and south coast areas (Fig. 1c). The C input in 2001–2020 based on $C_{in,yield\&livestock}$ ranges from 1.49 to 2.34 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ with an average of 2.05 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$ (Fig. 1d). The high C input is mainly located in west and southwest Finland and the low input is in north and east Finland (Fig. 1c). The C input based on $C_{in,yield\&livestock}$ is higher than that based on NPP_m approach on average by 0.42 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$. According to the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap, SOC stocks ranges from 44.49 to 155.04 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}$, with an average of 68.87 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}$ and a standard deviation of 28.14 $t\ C\ ha^{-1}$, in croplands across Finland in 2000 for soil depth of 0–30 cm (Fig. 2). The

Fig. 1. The estimated annual C input at equilibrium in 2000 (a), mean C input estimated based on NPP_m in 2001–2020 (b) and 2021–2040 (c), and the crop yield and livestock statistics at a prefecture level in 2001–2020 (d). The mean and standard deviation (sd) over the pixels are shown.

simulated SOC stocks in 2000 after the long spin up run are more or less equal to the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap which is ensured by the spin-up protocol (i.e., eq. 4).

3.2. Absolute SOC sequestration potential under BAU and three SSMs from 2021 to 2040

In the forward modeling from 2021 to 2040, with C input based on NPP_m and climate in 2001–2020 (Modeling experiment E1_{npp,0120}), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will averagely be $-0.03 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ with BAU, $-0.003 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ with SSM1, $0.03 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ with SSM2, and 0.08 t C ha^{-1}

Fig. 2. SOC stocks in 2000 according to the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap

yr⁻¹ with SSM3 (Fig. 3). With C input based on NPP_m in 2001–2020 but climate in 2021–2040 (Modeling experiment E2_{npp.2140}), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be averagely -0.23 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with BAU, -0.20 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM1, -0.18 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM2, and -0.12 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM3, because the impact of climate change will overtake that of C inputs on soil C change (Fig. 3). With C input based on the C_{in}_{yield&livestock} in 2001–2020 and climate in 2001–2020 (Modeling experiment E3_{yield.0120}), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be averagely 0.05 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with BAU, 0.09 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM1, 0.13 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM2, and 0.20 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM3 (Fig. 3). With C input based on the C_{in}_{yield&livestock} in 2001–2020 but climate in 2021–2040 (Modeling experiment E4_{yield.2140}), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be averagely -0.22 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with BAU, -0.19 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM1, -0.16 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM2, and -0.1 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM3, because the impact of climate change will overtake that of C inputs (Fig. 3). With C input based on NPP_m in 2021–2040 and climate in 2021–2040 (Modeling experiment

Fig. 3. Absolute SOC sequestration rate under BAU and three SSMs from 2021 to 2040 derived from the modeling experiment E1_{npp.0120}, E2_{npp.2140}, E3_{yield.0120}, E4_{yield.2140}, E5_{npp.2140}, and E6_{yield.2140}. The error bars represent the standard deviation across the pixels. Positive values indicate soils to be a C sink and negative values indicate soils to be a C source.

E5_{npp.2140}), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be on average -0.20 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with BAU, -0.17 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM1, -0.14 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM2, and -0.08 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM3, because the impact of climate change will overtake that of C inputs (Fig. 3). With C input based on the C_{in}_{yield&livestock} in 2021–2040 and climate in 2021–2040 (Modeling experiment E6_{yield.2140}), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be on average -0.03 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with BAU, 0.007 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM1, 0.05 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM2, and 0.13 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ with SSM3, under the integrated impacts of climate change and C input (Fig. 3).

The spatial patterns of absolute SOC sequestration potential under BAU and three SSMs from 2021 to 2040, relative to 2020, derived from the modeling experiment E1_{npp.0120} (Figs.S3a-d), E3_{yield.0120} (Figs.S3e-h), E5_{npp.2140} (Fig. 4a-d) and E6_{yield.2140} (Fig. 4e-h), are presented. According to the modeling experiment E1_{npp.0120}, the lowest SOC sequestration potential will be in southwest Finland and the highest will be in west Finland, SSMs will promote SOC sequestration most in south coast areas and west Finland (Figs.S3a-d). According to the modeling experiment E3_{yield.0120}, the SOC sequestration potential will be much higher than that of E1_{npp.0120} (Figs.S3e-h), although with a similar pattern. A broad area across Finland will change from SOC loss to SOC sequestration with SSM practices, particularly in south coast areas, west and southwest Finland (Figs.S3e-h). According to the modeling experiment E5_{npp.2140}, the SOC sequestration potential will be much reduced by climate change comparing to E1_{npp.0120} across the nation, although with a similar pattern. The SSM practices will offset cropland SOC loss to some extent but will not be able to turn it into SOC sequestration in most of Finland (Fig. 4a-d). According to the modeling experiment E6_{yield.2140}, the SOC sequestration potential will be much reduced comparing to E3_{yield.0120} (Fig. 4e-h, Figs.S3e-h), although with a similar pattern. A broad area across Finland will change gradually from SOC loss to SOC sequestration with C input increasing from SSM1 to SSM3, particularly in south coast areas and southwest Finland (Fig. 4e-h). In the meantime, the SOC sequestration potential in the west will become much larger with more C inputs.

3.3. Relative SOC sequestration potential in 2040 under three SSMs comparing to BAU

The ΔSOC_{RSR} under the SSM practices during 2021–2040, relative to BAU, derived from each modeling experiment, is presented in Fig. 5. For all the modeling experiments, the SSM practices will promote SOC sequestration measurably relative to BAU and increase it more with more C inputs. For example, the ΔSOC_{RSR} under SSM3 will be the largest, and the ΔSOC_{RSR} from a high C input (i.e., E3_{yield.0120}, E6_{yield.2140}) will be larger than that from a low C input (E1_{npp.0120}, E5_{npp.2140}). In addition, the ΔSOC_{RSR} will be reduced by climate change. For example, the ΔSOC_{RSR} from E2_{npp.2140} (E4_{yield.2140}) will be less than that from E1_{npp.0120} (E3_{yield.0120}) due to the impact of climate change. The integrated impacts of future climate change and agricultural management (E5_{npp.2140}, E6_{yield.2140}) on the ΔSOC_{RSR} will be dependent on the relative impact of C input and climate change. For example, the C input under E5_{npp.2140} will increase slightly under BAU comparing to E1_{npp.0120} and E2_{npp.2140}, as a result, the ΔSOC_{RSR} from E5_{npp.2140} will be larger than that from E2_{npp.2140} but smaller than that from E1_{npp.0120} owing to the larger impact of climate change than that of C input. By contrast, the C input under E6_{yield.2140} will increase by 1.22 times under BAU comparing to E3_{yield.0120} and E4_{yield.2140}, as a result, the ΔSOC_{RSR} from E6_{yield.2140} will be larger than that from E3_{yield.0120} and E4_{yield.2140} owing to the larger impact of C input than that of climate change (Fig. 5). According to E5_{npp.2140} (E6_{yield.2140}), the ΔSOC_{RSR} during 2021–2040 will averagely be 0.03 (0.04), 0.06 (0.08), and 0.11 (0.17) t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, respectively, under SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3, respectively.

The ΔSOC_{RSR} during 2021–2040 under SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 management scenarios, from E1_{npp.0120} (Figs.S4a, b, c), will have a similar pattern. It will be relatively high in west Finland but relatively

Fig. 4. Spatial patterns of absolute SOC sequestration potential under BAU and three SSMs from 2021 to 2040, relative to 2020, derived from the modeling experiment E5_nppyr.2140 (a, b, c, d) and E6_yieldyr.2140 (e, f, g, h).

Fig. 5. Relative SOC sequestration potential during 2021–2040 under SSM practices (SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3), comparing to BAU, derived from each modeling experiment.

low in south Finland. The ΔSOC_{RSR} under SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 management scenarios, from E3_{yield,0120} (Figs.S4d, e, f), will also have a similar pattern but different from E1_{npp,0120}. It will be relatively high in west and southwest Finland but relatively low in east Finland and the central part of south Finland. Under the integrated impacts of climate change and agronomic management, the ΔSOC_{RSR} under SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 management scenarios, from E5_{nppyr,2140} (Fig. 6a–c), will have a similar pattern to that from E1_{npp,0120} but with different values (Figs.S4a, b, c). The ΔSOC_{RSR} from E6_{yield,2140} (Fig. 6d–f) will have a similar pattern to that from E3_{yield,0120} but with different values (Figs. S4d, e, f).

3.4. Climate change, C input, and their integrated impacts on the absolute SOC sequestration during 2021–2040

Climate change impact on the ΔSOC_{ASR} during 2021–2040 is quantified by the simulated ΔSOC_{ASR} between E2_{npp,2140} and E1_{npp,0120}, and between E4_{yield,2140} and E3_{yield,0120} (Fig. 7). The ΔSOC_{ASR} will decline on average by 0.20 and 0.28 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ due to climate change impact, respectively, with the C input derived from NPP_m and the C_{in, yield&livestock}. C input impact on the ΔSOC_{ASR} is quantified by the simulated ΔSOC_{ASR} between E5_{nppyr,2140} and E2_{npp,2140}, and between E6_{yield,2140} and E4_{yield,2140} (Fig. 7). C input will promote ΔSOC_{ASR} on average by 0.033 (0.18), 0.035(0.20), 0.037(0.21), and 0.04 (0.23) t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ under BAU, SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3, respectively, with the C input derived from NPP_m (C_{in, yield&livestock}). The integrated impacts of climate change and C input on the ΔSOC_{ASR} are quantified by the simulated ΔSOC_{ASR} between E5_{nppyr,2140} and E1_{npp,0120}, and between E6_{yield,2140} and E3_{yield,0120}. With the C input derived from NPP_m (C_{in, yield&livestock}), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be reduced on average by 0.16(0.08), 0.16(0.08), 0.16 (0.08), and 0.17(0.07) t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ under BAU, SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3, respectively, due to the integrated impacts of climate change and C input (Fig. 7).

The spatial patterns of climate change, C input, and their integrated impacts on the ΔSOC_{ASR} during 2021–2040 under BAU, SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 are presented in Fig.S5 for C input derived from NPP_m and in Fig. 8 for C input derived from C_{in, yield&livestock}. The impact of climate change on the ΔSOC_{ASR} will have a similar pattern under BAU, SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3 (Figs.S5a,b,c,d; Figs. 8a–d). It will also have a similar pattern for C input derived from NPP_m (Figs.S5a,b,c,d) and C_{in, yield&livestock} (Fig. 8a–d). The impact of climate change on the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be relatively large in west Finland and south coast areas and relatively small in

southwest and east Finland, for C input derived from both NPP_m (Figs. S5a,b,c,d) and C_{in, yield&livestock} (Fig. 8a–d). The impact of C input on the ΔSOC_{ASR} will have a similar pattern under BAU, SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 (Figs.S5e,f,g,h; Fig. 8e–h), but have a different pattern between the C input based on NPP_m and C_{in, yield&livestock}. For the C input based on NPP_m, the largest impacts of C input on the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be located in south coast areas and southwest Finland, and the least in west Finland where NPP will be reduced by climate change (Figs.S5e,f,g,h). By contrast, for the C input based on the C_{in, yield&livestock}, the largest impacts of C input on the ΔSOC_{ASR} will be located in southwest and west Finland, and the least in north and east Finland (Fig. 8e–h). Again, the integrated impacts of climate change and C input on the ΔSOC_{ASR} will have a similar pattern under BAU, SSMs, SSM2, SSM3 and SSM4 (Figs.S5i,g,k,l; Fig. 8i–l), but have a different pattern between the C input based on NPP_m and C_{in, yield&livestock}. For the C input based on NPP_m, the integrated impacts will be mostly negative except for portions in southwest Finland, and the ΔSOC_{ASR} will decrease most by up to 0.3 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in west Finland (Figs.S5i,g,k,l). By contrast, for the C input based on the C_{in, yield&livestock}, the ΔSOC_{ASR} will increase most by around 0.1 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in southwest and portions of west Finland, but decrease most in south coast areas and portions of west Finland (Fig. 8i,g,k,l).

4. Discussion

4.1. The mechanisms underlying SOC sequestration for Finnish croplands

The results show that the SOC sequestration for mineral cropland soils in Finland over 2021–2040 will have a spatial explicit pattern which are subject to many factors including climate change, agricultural management, and their integrated impacts. The estimated SOC stock was the largest in southwest and west Finland and south coast areas in 2000 (Fig. 2) because soil clay content is the highest in these regions (Fig.S1). A recent meta-analysis show the silt and clay contents in soils as well as the clay mineralogy are the main factors affecting the maximal C storage levels of soils (Matus, 2021). A high soil clay content reduces the partitioning between CO₂ evolved and (BIO + HUM) formed during decomposition (Jenkinson et al., 1992; Jenkinson and Coleman, 1994), leading to less SOC loss from soil. Recent studies show that not only the C decomposability but also its interaction with soil mineralogy and climate, together with availability of nutrients and water, are controlling the actual decomposition (Doetterl et al., 2015). Soils with a high carbon content are characterized by substantial adsorption of carbon compounds onto mineral soil and low rates of respiration per unit of soil carbon. Precipitation and temperature affect carbon storage, respiration, residence time and stabilization mechanisms too (Doetterl et al., 2015), which may undermine SOC sequestration under future climate in the regions with low C input and low soil silt and clay contents as shown in this study. In 2021–2040, relative to 1981–2000, temperature will increase by 1.7–2.4 °C across Finland, with the largest increase in east Finland (Fig.S2b); precipitation will increase by 4.2–15.2%, with the least increase in southwest, west and south Finland (Fig.S2d). PET will increase by 0.8–83.1 mm per year across Finland, with the largest increase in southwest and south Finland (Fig.S2b). PET is projected to increase more than precipitation under climate change in west Finland which will aggravate drought stress, reduce NPP and consequently C input based on NPP_m. The major agricultural regions in southwest, south and west Finland will expect higher temperature and drier conditions, which explain well the projected negative impacts of climate change on the ΔSOC_{ASR} in these regions (Figs.S5a,b,c,d; Fig. 8a–d). In the RothC model, an increase in temperature accelerates the SOC decomposition rate exponentially and causes SOC loss from soil (Jenkinson et al., 1992; Jenkinson and Coleman, 1994). Impacts of precipitation on SOC decomposition rate depend on soil moisture deficit (Jenkinson et al., 1992; Jenkinson and Coleman, 1994). Besides, the projected impact of C input on the ΔSOC_{ASR} (Figs.S5e,f,g,h; Fig. 8e–h) is well consistent with the C input in 2001–2020 (Fig. 1a,c) and its projected change in

Fig. 6. Spatial patterns of the relative SOC sequestration potential during 2021–2040 under SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 management scenarios comparing to BAU, derived from the modeling experiment E5_{hpyr.2140} (a, b, c) and E6_{yieldr.2140} (d, e, f).

Fig. 7. Climate change ($E2_{npp.2140} - E1_{npp.0120}$, $E4_{yield.2140} - E3_{yield.0120}$), C input ($E5_{npp.2140} - E2_{npp.2140}$, $E6_{yield.2140} - E4_{yield.2140}$), and their integrated impacts ($E5_{npp.2140} - E1_{npp.0120}$, $E6_{yield.2140} - E3_{yield.0120}$) on the absolute SOC sequestration potential during 2021–2040.

2021–2040 under climate change (Fig. 1b).

The relative contribution of C input, temperature, and precipitation to the ΔSOC_{ASR} in 2021–2040 is further quantified (Fig. 9). Across the cropland in Finland, on average, the relative contribution of C input, temperature, and precipitation to the ΔSOC_{ASR} in 2021–2040 will be 56%, 24%, and 20%, respectively, however there is a spatially explicit pattern (Fig. 9). In west Finland, C input will be generally dominant for ΔSOC_{ASR} , where C input will be relatively high (Fig. 1) and climate change will be relatively mild (Fig. S2). In southwest Finland (Fig. 9), C input and temperature will be dominant for ΔSOC_{ASR} , where C input will be relatively high (Fig. 1), temperature is projected to increase moderately and precipitation is projected to increase slightly (Fig. S2). In south coast areas of Finland (Fig. 9), C input, temperature and precipitation will be dominant for ΔSOC_{ASR} , where C input will be moderate (Fig. 1), temperature is projected to increase slightly but precipitation is projected to increase substantially (Fig. S2). In north and east Finland (Fig. 9), temperature will be dominant for ΔSOC_{ASR} , where C input will be low (Fig. 1), temperature is projected to increase substantially and precipitation is projected to increase moderately (Fig. S2). In the central part of southern Finland, precipitation will be dominant for ΔSOC_{ASR} (Fig. 9), where precipitation will increase most and temperature will increase slightly and C input is project to be low. The results are well consistent with the findings based on the factorial simulation experiments (Figs. 7, 8, S5). Here, we compare the relative contribution of temperature, precipitation and C input using a statistical regression analysis based on the 40 simulations of RothC, taking account into the interactions of temperature, precipitation and C input. The statistical regression analysis of model outputs is sound to draw a general conclusion from the complex process-based simulations (e.g., Zhai et al., 2020). Although the SSMs have been defined as a relative change in C inputs and the C inputs are given a fixed rate, their interactions with environment and other factors are mechanically simulated by the process-based model RothC. The diverse modeling settings, the complex interactions of multiple factors, and the resultant large number of samples support the statistical regression analysis.

4.2. Comparisons with other studies

The results show that the SOC stocks in the top 30 cm ranged from 44.5 to 155.0 t C ha⁻¹ with an average of 68.9 t C ha⁻¹ for croplands on mineral soils across Finland in 2000 (Fig. 1). The SOC stocks in 2020 ranged from 53.4 to 155.6 (46.4–168.0) t C ha⁻¹ with an average of 76.4 (72.8) t C ha⁻¹ with the C input derived from $C_{in,yield\&livestock}$ (NPP_m). The results are generally supported by some previous studies based on

soil samples measurements (e.g., Heikkinen et al., 2013, 2021, 2022; de Brogniez et al., 2015; Lugato et al., 2015), considering the uncertainty from the quite different scales. For example, Heikkinen et al. (2013) showed that in mineral soils of Finland the mean C stocks varied between 41 and 67 t C ha⁻¹ in the top 15 cm over 1987–2009 depending on the management, soil class, and region. Heikkinen et al. (2021) showed that the SOC stock ranged from 70 to 115 t C ha⁻¹ with an average of 84–98 t C ha⁻¹ in the top 30 cm of Finnish agricultural mineral soils, based on soil samples at 125 plots in the Finnish national soil monitoring network. The findings of this study on the impacts of climate change and improved agricultural management are also corroborated by Heikkinen et al. (2022) based on soil samples collected nationwide in 2009 and 2018 in arable soil across Finland, which showed from 2009 to 2018 cropland SOC stock decreased by 0.067 and 0.296 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, respectively, due to an increase in precipitation and temperature. In comparison to annual-dominated rotation, SOC stock increased by about 0.241, 0.217, and 0.128 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for perennial, crop rotation, and diverse cropping system, respectively, owing to an increase in C input and decrease of tillage frequency (Heikkinen et al., 2022).

In addition, a map of the topsoil (0–20 cm) organic carbon content of Europe generated by a generalized additive model showed that SOC content in Finland ranged from 36 to >200 g C kg⁻¹ (de Brogniez et al., 2015). Using the CENTURY agroecosystem model, six alternative management practices scenarios were assessed as alternatives to BAU scenario across European arable soils (Lugato et al., 2015). The simulated SOC stock change in the topsoil layer (0–30 cm) by 2050 was projected to be 0.5–2.0 t C ha⁻¹ for crop residue management, 0.5–2.0 t C ha⁻¹ for reduced tillage, 2–5 t C ha⁻¹ for crop residue plus reduced tillage, 2–5 t C ha⁻¹ for ley in rotation, 1–10 t C ha⁻¹ for cover crops in Finland. The measured carbon sequestration rates derived from long-term experiments in literature ranged from about 0 to 0.5 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for all the tested management practices in the study (Lugato et al., 2015). A study using the Yasso07 model suggested SOC change would range from 0 to 0.3 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ over 2013–2040 depending on different cutting heights and harvesting strategies on the amounts of harvestable residue biomasses and allocation of residue biomasses in soil (Hakala et al., 2016). These studies did not take into account the impacts of future climate change, thus are comparable to our results from $E3_{yield.0120}$ that the ΔSOC_{ASR} will increase on average by 0.05, 0.09, 0.13, and 0.20 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, respectively, under the management scenario of BAU, SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 (Fig. 3).

4.3. Uncertainties and limitations in estimating the SOC sequestration potential

In this study, we quantify the uncertainties in estimating SOC sequestration from the main parameters affecting SOC dynamics for each SSM and climate change scenario as Eq. (17). As an example, the uncertainty in estimating SOC sequestration under GFDL climate scenario and SSM2 in the six modeling experiments is presented in Fig.S7. The uncertainty generally ranged from 10% to 20% in all the six modeling experiments. Future climate change will affect the spatio-temporal pattern of temperature and precipitation, as well as the frequency and intensity of climate extremes, and consequently crop productivity and SOC stocks (Tao et al., 2015). The current and projected climate change can adversely impact the terrestrial C stocks through increase in the rate of decomposition of organic matter and losses by accelerated erosion and other degradation processes (Lal, 2018). However, many previous studies did not take into account the impacts of future climate change (Lugato et al., 2015; FAO, 2020; Lounay et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2021). The Global assessment of SOC sequestration potential (GSOSeq) programme is to generate national SOC Sequestration Potential maps at 1 km resolution for croplands using the modeling settings of $E1_{npp.0120}$ or $E3_{yield.0120}$ applied in this study (FAO, 2020). These estimates without accounting the impacts of future climate change will overestimate the SOC sequestration potential as

Fig. 8. Spatial patterns of climate change ($E4_{\text{yield}.2140} - E3_{\text{yield}.0120}$, a,b,c,d), C input ($E6_{\text{yield}.2140} - E4_{\text{yield}.2140}$, e,f,g,h), and their integrated impacts ($E6_{\text{yield}.2140} - E3_{\text{yield}.0120}$, i,j,k,l) on the absolute SOC sequestration during 2021–2040, under BAU, SSM1, SSM2, and SSM3, respectively, with C input based on $C_{\text{in}}_{\text{yield}} \& \text{livestock}$.

Fig. 9. Spatial pattern of the dominant factors in controlling the SOC sequestration in 2021–2040 based on $E5_{nppyr.2140}$ and $E6_{yieldyr.2140}$.

shown in this study and a recent study on Germany (Riggers et al., 2021). In addition, the six modeling experiments with different settings of C inputs and climate scenarios allow us to quantify the relative contributions of main drivers, to look insights into mechanisms underlying SOC dynamics in various regions, and to understand the uncertainty in estimating SOC sequestration potential with different inputs. Nevertheless, several state-of-the-art process-based models should be applied to account for the uncertainties from model structure (Tao et al., 2018; Riggers et al., 2021), which could be larger than those from model input data (Grosz et al., 2017; Tao et al., 2018). This study focuses on the current croplands in Finland, historical land use change legacy (conversion from forest to cropland) is implicitly taken into account through the initial SOC stocks for the long spin-up run, the warm-up run, and the forward run. Historical land use influences the SOC content for decades after conversion to cropland. Nevertheless, in the fields with >100 years history of cultivation, the soils are apparently reaching a steady state and the changes in SOC content have leveled out (Heikkinen et al., 2022). Due to the limitations of the RothC model and lack of high-resolution spatiotemporal data on agronomic soil, crop and fertilizer management, the SSM scenarios are set as 5%, 10%, and 20% increase in C inputs, respectively, relative to BAU, considering the purposes of this study. This study can be further improved by extending the model analyses with explicit SSM scenarios that focus on agronomic soil, crop and fertilizer management based on realistic C inputs estimated from actual/desired practices and land use changes besides the different climatic scenarios. Spatially explicit SSM scenarios at 1 km resolution in the future are uncertain and not available so far. The spatiotemporal pattern of C inputs at 1 km resolution is critical but difficult to estimate at a large scale, which is feasible and sound to be estimated from the NPP map because C inputs are closely related to crop NPP (biomass) (FAO, 2020) but the uncertainties are originated from what proportions of the NPP are actually input to soils temporally and spatially by agricultural management. In addition, the estimates of total SOC stocks of 0–30 cm in the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap (FAO & ITPS, 2019) are used to inversely calibrate the C inputs, therefore the results rely on the accuracy of the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap to some extent. The FAO-ITPS GSOCmap is a compilation of SOC stock maps produced by member countries based on soil profiles/sampling data (FAO & ITPS, 2019). As shown in the

uncertainty analysis, an uncertainty coefficient of 20% for SOC from the FAO-ITPS GSOCmap is acceptable. The potential changes in soil properties such as bulk density due to agricultural management changes are not taken into account, which affect the SOC stocks estimates. Moreover, extreme climate events are often under-represented in future climate scenarios and not necessarily represented in monthly data. The impacts of future extreme climate events on SOC in croplands need to be further improved.

4.4. The implications of the SOC sequestration potentials

The results show that SOC has a spatially explicit pattern of the sequestration rates for croplands in Finland, which is subject to soil, climate, land cover and land management. In addition, the sequestration rates increase with carbon inputs, which, together with previous findings based on the long-term Finnish arable soil monitoring network (e.g., Heikkinen et al., 2022), suggest the agronomic management practices that increase carbon inputs should be encouraged politically and economically to increase SOC stocks (Lugato et al., 2015). Climate change will accelerate SOC decomposition substantially and an increase in C input will be needed to prevent SOC loss from climate change (Heikkinen et al., 2013). Under the integrated impacts of climate change and C input in 2021–2040 (Modeling experiment $E6_{yieldyr.2140}$), the ΔSOC_{ASR} will change on average by -0.03 ($-0.04\% \text{ yr}^{-1}$), 0.007 ($0.009\% \text{ yr}^{-1}$), 0.05 ($0.07\% \text{ yr}^{-1}$), and 0.13 ($0.17\% \text{ yr}^{-1}$) $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, respectively, under the management scenario of BAU, SSM1, SSM2 and SSM3 (Fig. 3). This means that adopting the SSM3 practices will turn Finnish agricultural soils into C sink, but not be enough to achieve the 4 per 1000 aspirational target for soil carbon over 2021–2040. In France, a 30%–40% increase in C inputs to soil will be needed to obtain a 4‰ increase per year over a 30-year period (Martin et al., 2021). A >40% increase in C inputs will be needed in Finland considering that a 20% increase in C inputs will lead to a 0.17% increase per year over 2021–2040.

This study provides general information on where and how much SOC could be sequestered with SSMs for croplands on mineral soils across Finland at 1 km resolution. For each pixel, we quantify the SOC sequestration potential over 2021–2040 under different scenarios of climate change and SSM practices, as well as the dominant factor in controlling the SOC sequestration potential. Such information is important for stakeholders to precisely manage croplands and enhance SOC sequestration. For example, the west and southwest Finland (Fig. 4e–h, Fig. 6d–f) are identified as the priority areas to be targeted for actions. In the regions where SOC sequestration is dominated by climate, such as north and east Finland, and the central part of southern Finland (Fig. 9), C input is quite low, increasing C input, for example, by developing mixed crop-livestock systems, will increase SOC sequestration efficiently. Moreover, although the SOC sequestration rates will increase with C inputs, the SOC sequestration efficiency of C input will be different spatially and among different SSMs (Figs. 3–6), which is valuable for stakeholders to develop cost-effective agricultural management practices for a certain region. Based on this information, stakeholders may further identify the optimal agricultural management practices for each pixel to increase C input and realize the SSM scenarios. There have been extensive studies on how to improve agricultural management practices (crop system diversification, conservation farming, and use of cover crop, composts/farmyard manure or other organic inputs) to increase C input. The findings of this study should be further associated with explicit SSM scenarios that focus on agronomic soil, crop and fertilizer management, based on realistic C inputs estimated from actual/desired practices, to manage cropland toward climate-smart agriculture. A combination of modeling and field experiment is valuable to increase C storage efficiently. For Finland, agricultural management practices to reduce soil C loss and increase the retention of soil C have been indicated through cultivation of perennial crops, adopting no-till or reduced tillage, applying organic manure,

adopting crop rotation, cover crop, and diverse cropping system. Adding forest residue biochar to soils can significantly increase carbon stored in soil and offer a chance to increase SOC stocks (Soenne et al., 2020). Expansion of mixed crop-livestock systems is a potential option for Finland too. In addition, climate change will ameliorate thermal and water resources at broad regions of Finland, adapting to climate change by adopting crop cultivars with a longer growth period and increasing winter crops and cover crops will be promising for enhancing SOC sequestration and enhancing the synergies of climate change adaptation and mitigation. Previous studies showed perennial, crop rotation, and diverse cropping system enriched topsoil SOC compared with dominantly annual crops which exhibited a less steep carbon gradient with depth (Heikkinen et al., 2013, 2022). Increasing carbon input by applying organic manure and avoiding bare fallow are means to slow down the loss of SOC (Akujärvi et al., 2014). Although the potential to accumulate SOC under no-till or reduced tillage compared to conventional tillage seems to be limited in boreal agroecosystems, the redistribution of SOC to the more stable conditions within the aggregates indicates positive impacts of no-till practice (Sheehy et al., 2015). Regionally customized carbon-farming programs are one way to tailor soil carbon storage to local conditions. A recent study on 105 Finnish farms showed most soil samples had considerable nutrient deficiencies (P, S, B and Mn), which limited crop growth and SOC accumulation (Mattila et al., 2022). The largest C storage potential was estimated for measures with large additions of nutrient-poor amendments or in grazing. Therefore, managing agroecosystem in a holistic way with systemic thinking is necessary.

This study focuses on mineral soils, but sustainable peatland management should also be considered in Finland, because about 60% of agricultural GHG emissions come from peatlands, which account for 11% of arable land under cultivation. The GHG emissions per hectare are several folds on peat soils compared to mineral soils. Peat soils are a dominant source of agriculture-related CO₂ and N₂O emissions at the country scale (Regina et al., 2019). Emissions can be reduced in both productive and non-productive croplands on peat soils with a number of measures, such as reduced cultivation of annual plants, controlled drainage, restoration, and paludiculture to maintain a high water level. The GHG mitigation potential from organic soils should be quantified and mapped for targeting GHG mitigation (Kekkonen et al., 2019).

5. Conclusions

The information as to which regions, environments and agricultural systems could have a potential for SOC sequestration, and which SSM practices are the most suitable and cost-efficient for a specific environment, is essential for policy-makers and land managers. In this study, we apply the RothC model, together with various local high resolution datasets, to investigate the SOC sequestration potential over 2021–2040 under different scenarios of climate change and SSM practices. Based on the results of the study, a 20% increase in C inputs to soil will turn Finnish agricultural soils into C sink, but not be enough to obtain a 4‰ increase per year over the 20-year period in Finland. C input will promote ΔSOC_{ASR} , however climate change will reduce it. The integrated impacts of climate change and C input will reduce it on average by 0.16 (0.08) t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, with the C input derived from NPP_m (C_{in}yield&live-stock). Across the cropland in Finland, on average, the relative contribution of C input, temperature, and precipitation to the ΔSOC_{ASR} in 2021–2040 will be 56%, 24%, and 20%, respectively, however there is a spatially explicit pattern. The SOC sequestration potential will be relatively high and dominated by C input in west and southwest Finland. By contrast, it will be relatively low and dominated by climate in north and east Finland, and the central part of southern Finland. The local environment-specific best management practices that increase carbon inputs should be encouraged politically and economically to realize the SOC sequestration potential. The processes and mechanisms on the SOC sequestration for different soil types and properties need to be further

investigated. An improved monitoring, data-collecting and modeling platform that integrates long-term experiments, remote sensing, spatiotemporal datasets (e.g., climate, soils and land cover), agricultural management practices, and SOC/GHG modeling across scales will be critical to enhance SOC sequestration and support soil sustainable management.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2023.103671>.

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